

Introducing Transformative Pedagogies in Teaching and Learning of the English Language: A Strategy for Educational Sustainability

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Abstract: The shift from traditional classrooms to digital platforms has transformed language acquisition in the 21st century, making sustainability education more critical than ever. This theoretical study examines the intersection of education and sustainability within the context of English language teaching and learning. It explores how transformative pedagogies can support sustainable practices in an evolving technological landscape. The first section defines sustainability education, outlining its goals and the importance of equipping students with the linguistic skills to address complex environmental, social, and economic challenges. However, integrating sustainability into language instruction poses challenges, such as aligning sustainability topics with language learning objectives. This work highlights these issues and their societal implications, stressing the need to redesign educational systems with sustainability at the forefront. The study proposes transformative pedagogical strategies that educators and policymakers can adopt to foster a generation of socially and ecologically conscious global citizens. Ultimately, it offers practical recommendations for integrating sustainability into curricula, guiding stakeholders in navigating the challenges posed by technological disruption in language education.

Keywords: Transformative pedagogy, education for sustainability, English language, teaching and learning

Introduction

The English language has become the most widely used language worldwide in recent decades. The language is among the most extensively spoken across a variety of global contexts. As such, it is among the world's global languages in addition to being an international language. It is important to remember that there are various applications of the language which includes: speaking English as a first language, second language, or foreign language. English is spoken by individuals such as academics, businesspeople, and communicators all over the world for a variety of purposes.

As a result, sustainability in language instruction has received increased attention due to the global importance of the language. Furthermore, the fact that language is seen as a dynamic and adaptable subject have become more prevalent (Larsen-Freeman 2019). The need to incorporate education for sustainability into the curricula is now a trending issue in language instruction. The learning process of sustainable development has been proposed to be facilitated by a comprehensive strategy that addresses the environmental, economic, social, and cultural aspects of sustainability (Minna, 2023). The significance of sustainability in language learning given the speed at which technology is developing cannot be overemphasized.

Therefore, the incorporation of sustainability in English Language Teaching (ELT) offers a singular opportunity that transcends more than just picking up vocabulary and grammar; it's a strong instrument for influencing

attitudes, behaviours, and perceptions (Bektesh, 2020). By adopting sustainability-focused English language teaching (ELT), educators can use the platform to foster sustainable practices and environmental activism across cultural barriers (Edwards, 2016).

Before this era of digitalization, the English language was taught for communication, not sustainability. Now, the world is advancing scientifically and education for sustainability has come to stay. Based on this premise, sustainability must be incorporated into ELT for several reasons. First, solutions to global environmental problems must go beyond national boundaries (Al Amin, 2018). Secondly, English is a potent communication tool for tackling problems cooperatively because, it is one of the world's official languages (Calvert, 2015). Usually, subjects related to sustainability provide a rich and genuine environment for language acquisition (Tuyan, 2018). Furthermore, addressing issues like loss of biodiversity, global warming, equitable growth, thinking critically, solving problems, and student engagement can all be enhanced by ELT. When the above is done, it will result in further in-depth education.

Additionally, incorporating environmental sustainability into ELT is in line with the larger educational objectives of creating global citizens who are aware of and actively involved in addressing the planet's most serious issues. This is backed up by the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations, especially SDG 4 and SDG 13, which seek to address global climate change, provide inclusive and equitable access to high-quality education, and encourage lifetime learning opportunities for all (Römhild, 2022). Sustainability education, or Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), has become more popular in light of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which is broadly supported by political leaders worldwide (Sandri and Holdsworth 2021). In addition to aiming for pedagogical quality, sustainability education should also develop transformative learning experiences in ELT.

In line with the above, Hegarty and Holdsworth (2015) and Taimur (2020) talked about the importance of inclusion of environmental education in ELT. They introduced the concept of "praxis" or "pedagogical" part of environmental education which they defined as the creation of a welcoming learning environment based on the teaching philosophy of the instructor. On the other hand, the dissemination of environmental content is referred to as "sustainability education".

In 1978, Jack Mezirow propounded the theory of transformative learning. Subsequently, the theory developed "into a thorough and intricate explanation of how students create, justify, and reinterpret the meaning of their experiences." The author conducted three systemically linked qualitative studies in collaboration with educators from the National University of Ireland in Galway, Ireland, King's College London, Boston College, Massachusetts, and nearby post-primary schools. These studies gave rise to the concept of "transformative language pedagogy" or "transformative pedagogy." By supporting the social-psychological model of independent language acquisition and teaching with an intercultural and moral-philosophical basis, transformative pedagogy improves it.

However, the gaps in teaching and learning of English language for education for sustainability include lack of integration with sustainability education, limited vocabulary and critical thinking skills, inadequate cultural relevance, overemphasis on grammar, and limited authentic materials. Additionally, teacher training and assessment methods may not align with sustainability education goals. Addressing these gaps can enhance English language instruction and foster a more informed and engaged global citizenry, better equipped to discuss and address sustainability challenges. This is the major reason that aroused the interest of the researcher to work on

this theoretical paper because it will address those challenges identified above and it will certainly help the target language instructors and learners to create a more comprehensive professional identity that combines leadership, practitioner-researcher, and other facets.

Understanding Sustainability Education

The phrase “sustainability and education” serves as the foundation for the idea of sustainability education. The Latin words ‘sustinere’ and ‘educatio’ are the sources of the English term’s “sustainability” and “education,” respectively. According to Jeronen (2013), the society, the environment, and the economy are all balanced in order to improve people's quality of life. However, this assertion was later proven not to be correct. Instead, there is the need for learning to improve one’s capacity by cultivating the capacity for logic and discernment, and mentally readying oneself or others for life (Thesaurus 2021). A true mental and behavioural shift is necessary to address many of the issues facing modern society and promote sustainable living.

Durability Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) is a term that is frequently used to refer to education. According to UNESCO (2014), ESD is “education for sustainable development that allows every human being to acquire the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values necessary to shape a sustainable future.” Thus, enabling individuals to make choices and take activities that enhance their quality of life without endangering the environment which is the goal and objective of ESD. Additionally, it seeks to include sustainable development values into all facets and educational levels. The three essential components that are crucial to the success of sustainability education in the classroom are abilities, attitudes, and knowledge. Using information exchange, attitude cultivation, and skill enhancement, sustainability education can serve as a potent instrument in fostering resilient communities capable of confronting contemporary environmental issues.

Examining the body of research on sustainable education in general is appropriate. Based on the findings, it is observed that ELT is among the essential competencies for developing “sustainability citizens.” Prior studies on sustainability education have concentrated on sustainability competencies (Evans 2019; Rieckmann 2018; Wiek & Lang 2016). A list of shared competencies for managing wicked problems—open-ended, contested issues—has been compiled by ESD scholars (Hull et al. 2018; Marouli 2021). They connected it to climate change, inequality, and the degradation of the environment. Among these sustainable competencies are critical, creative, and systems thinking (i.e. an awareness of links, and interdisciplinarity). It is evident from their statements that transformative learning aims to alter both the learner and broader societal structures by questioning social norms within institutions.

However, research findings from the above indicate that students lacked the necessary motivation to change their living conditions and the culture they inhabit, even when it is a straightforward act of raising awareness about sustainability (Blenkinsop & Morse, 2017). Thus, in addition to emphasizing learner-centred outcomes (expressed in terms of competencies), Herranen et al. (2018) have argued that active and learner-driven approaches are also essential components of ESD. Before power structures can be significantly reorganized, learner-driven curricula encourage students to become agents or actors who can define sustainability and put into practice workable sustainable practices through an iterative process. Furthermore, Stains et al. (2018), opined that a lot of sustainability education, including ESD, still follow the norm of a transmissive and instrumentalist teaching/learning method, which is common in many academic fields. Transmissive teaching also referred to as “transformative,” is based on the idea that teachers have a body of knowledge that can be easily and directionally transferred to students to “transform” sustainability-related

problems.

In conclusion, criticality plays a significant role in enlivening a transformational pedagogy, and sustainability education is probably primarily motivated by its potential for transformation. However, while scholars have tried to outline the general features of transformative learning—such as its characteristics—few have elaborated on how it can be operationalized, and many have not yet found a way to apply transformative pedagogy to the teaching and learning of English in a way that promotes sustainability in education.

The Teaching and Learning of the English Language

In present-day Nigeria, the ability of an individual to speak English very well is becoming a necessary tool for progress and advancement. Historically, the English language started when three Germanic tribes: the Angles, the Saxons, and the Jutes, crossed the North Sea and arrived in Britain in the fifth century AD from what is now northern Germany and Denmark. The language spoken by the people of Britain was a Celtic language prior to the three Germanic tribes' invasion. But soon after the invasion, the language that had only been used in Britain since the fifth century spread throughout the country and is now growing rapidly.

Language has unique qualities, one of the language's fundamental qualities in this modern era is the simplicity of inflections. The other two are the language's flexibility of function and open vocabulary. Because of the absence of inflections, function has become more flexible during the past 500 years. Words that were once identified as verbs or nouns based on variations in their forms are now frequently employed in both contexts. For instance, one can discuss organizing a table or tabling an agenda, reserving a space or setting a book, or thumbing an elevator. Due to technological advancement, Virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR), two contemporary technologies, are now included in introductory English-speaking classes. Language labs, online learning environments, digitalization, multimedia devices, mobile phones, learning applications, flashcards, audio/visual multimedia content (such as podcasts and videos), EdTech solutions, artificial intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IOT), automation, and social media are examples of modern language teaching and learning technology. One of the main benefits of technology is that it has given students more autonomy and satisfaction.

Transformative pedagogies in English language teaching and learning prioritize critical literacy, student agency, inclusive materials, collaborative learning, reflective practice, and process-oriented approaches to empower learners to challenge dominant discourses, promote social justice, and foster critical thinking. By integrating language learning with real-world social and environmental issues, such as sustainability and equality, this approach values creativity, experimentation, and collective problem-solving over standardized outcomes. Through transformative pedagogies, English language education becomes a powerful tool for personal and societal transformation, encouraging learners to analyze, question, and shape their worlds, and preparing them to engage actively in creating a more just and equitable society.

The English language education system has a wide range of social effects and benefits. It has affected economies, industries, and the education system as a whole. It is a language that is used to promote tourism and acts as the primary language used in scientific research. English language is the language of the Internet; it is a means of international communication and dialogue, increases job opportunities and is also the language that is used to transfer cultures. It is required in the majority of schools worldwide. Many businesses, science, and opportunities across societies are driven by English Language. English Language has influenced every aspect of modern life, from science and culture to education and even shopping. Its effects are long-lasting and will probably intensify as humanity continues to integrate into the global economy.

In summary, the teaching and learning of English language involves a dynamic and interactive process, where learners acquire language skills through exposure, practice, and authentic experiences. Effective instruction incorporates diverse materials, technology, and collaborative activities, catering to various learning styles and needs. As learners engage with the language, they develop reading, writing, speaking, and listening skills, enabling them to communicate effectively and confidently in real-world contexts. Through a supportive and inclusive learning environment, learners become proficient in English, unlocking opportunities for personal, academic, and professional growth.

Challenges and Opportunities in Education

There are numerous difficulties encountered when teaching English, particularly in the Nigerian context. Among these are problems with the alignment of language learning objectives with sustainability concerns, a dearth of technological devices, network outages, and a shortage of materials that energize the classroom and spark students' imaginations. According to Harumi (2011), the majority of teachers face difficulties as a result of inadequate and inappropriate teaching resources, which inhibit English language instruction and acquisition.

Another issue that most English teachers deal with is the attitudinal approach, which includes students' lack of dedication and attitude towards the language comprehension, and their belief that English is one of the hardest subject to learn. Some factor arises from the teacher's side like teachers' selective attention that makes students feel discriminated against, teaching in classrooms that are too small or crowded, using outdated English textbooks, using unfamiliar words, and lacking context in the curriculum mitigates against ELT (Cummins, 2017).

Opportunity varies in ELT because there are tons of opportunities to incorporate sustainability education into the teaching of English. This is evident in the fact that the English language facilitates students' acquisition of several competencies, including anticipatory competency, collaboration competency, systems thinking competency, strategic competency, critical thinking competency, and self-awareness competency. Speaking on the roles of educators and policymakers in modifying education to achieve sustainability goals, governments all over the world have realized that significant policy and practice changes are necessary to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education, which is UNESCO's Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4. Localities have tried to achieve this in several ways, including enacting laws mandating diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) professional development for current teachers and incorporating DEI training into pre-service preparation programs. Policies have also been designed to intentionally hire a greater diversity of teachers in ELT (Smith & Heyward, 2024).

Framework for Transformative Pedagogies in Teaching of English Language for Educational Sustainability

The Burns model as developed in 1978 can be used to understand the pedagogical approach to teaching sustainability in English and in a technologically advanced environment. A useful and flexible approach for teaching sustainability in a range of settings, such as academic courses, extracurricular activities, student leadership initiatives, and non-formal education, is the Burns approach of Sustainability Pedagogy.

According to Burns (2009), the model acknowledges that when it comes to creating sustainable and regenerative educational systems, natural systems themselves are our finest teachers. Specifically, for higher education settings, this model integrates theories and best practices for teaching sustainability in an efficient manner. Offering chances for transformative learning that inspire and push students to reevaluate their values and make

real, lasting changes in their own lives as well as in their communities and environments is the main objective of the Burns' model. Burns' model consists of five crucial dimensions namely Content which comes first, followed by perspectives, process, context, process, and design.

Talking about previous case studies for this paper, an example is Swansea, Wales, The Down to Earth Project is an award-winning not-for-profit social company that serves as a realistic case study of a successful sustainability education effort. Thousands of marginalized and vulnerable adults and youth have participated in the initiative since its founding in 2006, helping to alleviate social inequalities and promote sustainability in the neighbourhood. This creative effort shows how disadvantaged people can benefit from education for sustainability. It doesn't have to be "taught," but it may be practically applied to show and offer a means of escaping poverty, creating connections, and fostering a sense of community (Alex, 2019).

Arizona State University (ASU): ASU is well-known for its multidisciplinary degree offerings and School of Sustainability. The university has put in place several environmental measures, such as zero-waste campaigns, solar energy installations, and sustainable mobility plans. Furthermore, the Sustainability Initiative at the University of British Columbia (UBC) incorporates sustainability into both academic and operational domains. The university has committed to becoming carbon-neutral and integrating sustainability into campus planning and curriculum development. Lesson plans, activities, and teaching resources are available on educational websites and platforms like National Geographic Education and Eco-Schools to help educators integrate sustainability principles into their teaching practices. Having seen the practicability of sustainability in education, this paper proposes the introduction of transformative pedagogy in ELT.

Leveraging Technology for Sustainable Education

When it comes to utilizing technology for sustainable education, gamification, simulations, and multimedia can all help to make sustainability education more dynamic and engaging. Students can engage in virtual reality scenarios, play games, or view videos that demonstrate the effects and solutions to sustainability challenges. An instance of cutting-edge tools that promote sustainability education is the application of sustainable technology to lessen our reliance on fossil fuels and minimize greenhouse gas emissions using wind energy, solar energy, and hydropower. There are also potential risks and ethical considerations when technology is introduced for sustainability education. Some of the risks include resistance to change, security risks, high market competition, limited budget, addiction to social media platforms, etc.

However, technology can be leveraged for sustainable education in English language teaching and learning through online resources, digital language learning platforms, virtual classrooms, educational multimedia, and collaboration tools. These tools reduce paper waste, promote accessibility, and increase global connectivity, while also providing personalized, self-paced learning experiences. Additionally, digital materials can focus on sustainable themes, and virtual reality and gamification can enhance immersive learning experiences. By embracing technology, English language education can become more sustainable, inclusive, and engaging, ultimately promoting a more environmentally conscious and connected global community.

Building a Sustainable Future: Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

Having recognized the value of transformative pedagogies toward education sustainability in English language instruction, the researcher advises policymakers, educators, and other education stakeholders to incorporate this innovative idea into the curriculum considering global challenges and responsibilities. This will help students

develop a sustainable mindset and, more importantly, prepare them to meet the demands of a changing world and successfully navigate the complexities of language acquisition in the twenty-first century.

One way to promote interdisciplinary cooperation in the classroom is by giving students access to a wide range of possibilities for learning across disciplines. Multi-disciplinary collaborative projects can improve learning and give students practical experience. It is crucial to note that the direction of education for sustainability suggests that it will be crucial in forming a more sustainable future by providing students with the knowledge, attitudes, and values needed to make a positive impact on a more sustainable world. Additionally, it will promote sustainable habits, allowing students to become aware of and involved in the most important global issues. Additionally, it will support possibilities for lifelong learning for everyone, guarantee inclusive and equitable quality education, and combat global climate change.

Introducing transformative pedagogies in the teaching and learning of the English language is a vital strategy for Education for Sustainability. By empowering learners to critically engage with social and environmental issues, fostering inclusive and participatory learning environments, and leveraging technology for sustainable education, we can cultivate a new generation of global citizens equipped to address the complex challenges of the 21st century. As we transform the way we teach and learn English, we can unlock the full potential of language education to promote a more just, equitable, and sustainable world.

Future Directions and Implications - Recommendations

As we move forward, the integration of transformative pedagogies in English language teaching and learning for Education for Sustainability will continue to evolve driving innovation in curriculum design, teacher professional development, and technology-enhanced learning. This will enable learners to develop the knowledge, skills, and agency needed to address the complex sustainability challenges of the 21st century.

The implications of this work are profound, with the potential to transform English language education into a powerful catalyst for personal, social, and environmental transformation. By harnessing the power of language learning to promote sustainability, we can empower a global community of change-makers, equipped to shape a more just, equitable, and sustainable future for all.

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